

The Impact of Age, Gender, Education Level, And Income on The Organizational Commitment of Young Workers in Vietnam

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Abstract

This study measures the level of organizational commitment and assesses the impact of age, gender, education level, and income on the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam. A quantitative, cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted on a sample of 311 workers under 30 years old who were randomly selected and conveniently selected. A self-report questionnaire was used to collect data, and the research data were processed using SPSS 26.0 software. The research results show that the organizational commitment of young workers is above average; age, education level, and monthly income have a positive impact on their organizational commitment. The results of this study provide a practical and scientific basis for planning and implementing policies and measures related to age, gender, education level, and income of workers in human resource management of organizations to improve the level of organizational commitment of young workers.

Keywords: *Organizational Commitment, Age, Gender, Education Level, Income, Young Workers, Vietnam.*

INTRODUCTION

The workforce is one of the important resources that determines the survival of organizations and businesses (Shaker et al., 2020; Nicolás-Agustín et al., 2022; Parinsi & Moses, 2023; Horváth-Csikós et al., 2023). Possessing an abundant and high-quality workforce will create a competitive advantage for businesses, especially in the current fiercely competitive context (Saleh et al., 2020; Agit et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2024; Rudihartati & Dwiono, 2025). The workforce of a business is often divided into many groups, in which young workers account for a fairly high proportion (Irene et al., 2022; Tuan et al., 2025). Young workers are characterized by a spirit of entrepreneurial spirit, self-challenge, desire for recognition, and social contribution (Ayoobzadeh et al., 2024; Zholdasbekova et al., 2024). They will be an important resource for the long-term and sustainable development of the organization (Sundstrup et al., 2024).

Attracting and effectively managing the workforce in general and young workers in particular will bring great benefits to businesses, helping businesses operate effectively and creating a premise for long-term and sustainable development (Okoye & Raymond, 2013; Mohanad, 2019; Lam, 2023; Djunaedi, 2025). Managing young workers in enterprises today has posed many challenges, in which the problem of their frequent job-hopping and job-quitting has significantly impacted the performance of enterprises (Dwidienawati, 2022; Trang et al., 2023; Maharani, 2023; Lam, 2023). Therefore, promoting the commitment and long-term attachment to the organization of young workers is one of the important, urgent, and necessary tasks (Bińczycki et al., 2023; Islamiyah & Pratama, 2023; Didit et al., 2024; Mardikaningsih, 2024).

Organizational commitment is considered one of the important psychological resources in employees, demonstrating a sense of responsibility, desire to stick with and contribute, thereby promoting participation and effort at work (Porter et al., 1974; Lalit et al., 2005; Jyoti et al., 2021). Commitment and attachment to the organization strongly influence employee performance and greatly impact business performance (Andrew, 2017; Saragih, 2017; Suharto et al., 2019; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022). There have been many different studies on employee organizational commitment (Nabhan & Munajat, 2023; Motsaathebe & Molefi, 2025; Muhammad Shohib & Agustina, 2024); the relationship between organizational commitment and other psychological factors such as work motivation, income satisfaction, job engagement, and turnover intention (Francisco & Maria, 2017; Neves et al., 2022; Pramitha, 2024; Maarif et al., 2024). However, studies on organizational commitment in young workers are limited, especially studies exploring the impact of age, gender, education level, and income on the organizational commitment of young employees in the context of Vietnam. This study was conducted to confirm the relationship between age, gender, education level, and income of young workers with their organizational commitment, thereby providing a scientific and practical basis for planning and implementing policies and measures related to age, gender, education level, and income of workers in human resource management to enhance the level of commitment to the organization of young employees, contribute to ensuring sustainable development of organizations and businesses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is a widely studied topic in the fields of human resource management and organizational behavior (Akehurst et al., 2009). It affects employee behavior in organizations (Mowday et al., 1979) and reflects positive employee behavior in organizations (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001; Meyer et al., 2002). This is a complex concept, analyzed by researchers from many different perspectives: organizational commitment as a binding force, shaping employees' behavior with organizational goals (Meyer and Herscovitch, 2001), as a promise of attachment to work, loyalty to the organization (Northcraft & Neale, 1996; Cohen, 2007), it shows the level of commitment to the organization's goals, the desire to stay with the organization for a long time (Robbins, 2013) or pride in belonging to an organization (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Meyer and Allen (1991) considered commitment as a psychological state reflecting the relationship between employees and the organization, and is reflected in three aspects: emotional attachment, maintenance attachment, and obligation/moral attachment. Dung (2005) identified organizational commitment as the strength of consensus between individuals and the common goals and values of the organization, expressed by active participation in the organization and including three components of pride, effort, and loyalty to the organization. Luthans et al. (2007) considered organizational commitment as an important component of employees' psychological resources. Studies show that organizational commitment has a strong impact on employee motivation (Qendrim, 2020; Putri & Setyo, 2020), affects their work performance and outcomes (Chen et al., 2006; Loan, 2020; Putri & Setyo, 2020; Munda, 2024), influences job satisfaction (Chughtai & Zafar, 2006; Shahid & Azhar, 2013) and organizational citizenship behavior (Zeinabadi & Salehi, 2011), organizational commitment also affects turnover intention and organizational stability (Wright & Bonett, 2007; Khan et al., 2014; Belete, 2018; Lestari & Margaretha, 2021).

Factors affecting organizational commitment

Studies on this issue confirm that there are many different factors affecting employees' organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is the result of personal variables, role statuses, and variables belonging to the working environment (Mathieu and Zajac, 1990). Some studies emphasize the role of job satisfaction. Fu et al. (2011) argued that job satisfaction is the initial condition for organizational commitment; employees will be more committed and contribute more to the organization when they feel satisfied with their job and the income they receive (Ha, 2016; Meithiana, 2018; Giao & Hoanh, 2019; Nicolas & Setyo, 2020). Several other studies confirm the role of work motivation; employees with stronger work motivation are often more committed to the organization and vice versa (Blau, 1986; Blau & Boal, 1987; Meysam & Ali, 2013; Qëndrim, 2020; Nurlina et al., 2023). Personality traits are also thought to influence employees' behavior, attitudes, and organizational commitment (Judge et al., 2002; Erdheim et al., 2006; Jabari et al., 2013; Nam & Lan, 2021). Kumar & Bakhshi (2010) found that extraversion is positively correlated with affective commitment, and neuroticism is negatively correlated with affective commitment. Studies by Cheng & Chew (2004), Dung (2009), Anh and Dao (2013), Ha (2016) confirm the influence of factors related to the work environment on employees' organizational commitment such as: job characteristics, salary, rewards and recognition, training and career development, career opportunities, leadership behavior, organizational culture and policies, work environment, decision-making rights, performance appraisal, and relationships within the organization. Several studies have also explored the influence of demographic characteristics, age, gender (Lalit et al., 2005; Sangeeta, 2018; Gönül & Osman, 2018; Ashraf, 2020; Raymond et al., 2024; Adamchik & Sedlak, 2024), education level, and income (Ariffin & Ha, 2015; González et al., 2016; Li & Chen, 2021; Novlinda et al., 2018; Katebi et al., 2025) on employees' organizational commitment. However, studies on these factors have not been conducted much in the context of Vietnam.

METHODOLOGY

Research Objectives and Hypotheses

The objective of this study is to measure the level of organizational commitment and explore the impact of age, gender, education level, and income on the organizational commitment of young workers in the context of Vietnam. There are two research hypotheses that need to be addressed:

H1: Organizational commitment of young workers is at an average level.

H2: Age, gender, education level, and income have an impact on the organizational commitment of young workers.

Research Design

A quantitative, cross-sectional descriptive study was used in this study. Based on the overview and research context, the research objectives and hypotheses were established. The research participants were recruited to provide information through questionnaire responses at one point in time. The data obtained from the questionnaire survey will then be processed using statistical software, through which the research hypotheses will be tested.

Participants

According to Hair's (2014) sampling approach, the minimum sample size is 50 participants for research using EFA. The larger the number of participants, the higher the reliability. To ensure the effectiveness of the research conclusions, we conducted a survey of 350 participants, who were young workers (under 30 years old) with 3 years of continuous working experience up to the time of the survey, currently working for organizations and enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam and were selected by random, convenient sampling. Through preliminary testing, there were 311 valid responses, which were included in data processing.

Data collection tools

Research data were collected through a questionnaire including the following scales:

Organizational Commitment Scale

Based on Meyer and Allen's (1991) theory of 3-component model of organizational commitment, and through consulting experts and researchers in this field, we used a scale of 15 observed variables to measure 3 dimensions reflecting employees' organizational commitment: Affective commitment (07 items); Continuance commitment (04 items); Normative commitment (04 items). The observed variables were measured on a 5-point Likert scale: 1. Completely disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. No opinion, 4. Agree, 5. Completely agree. The higher the score, the higher the organizational commitment. Some researchers in Vietnam have also approached Meyer and Allen's 03-component perspective in their studies on Employee Organizational Commitment (Phuong et al., 2021; Nam & Lan, 2021; Tuan et al., 2025). Cronbach's Alpha = 0.946 from the data of this study continues to confirm the reliability and appropriateness of the scale.

Age scale: The age of the research participants is measured through a scale consisting of 02 values corresponding to 02 age groups: 1. Under 25 years old; 2. From 25 to under 30 years old.

Gender scale: We use a scale consisting of 03 values: 1. Male; 2. Female; 3. Other gender.

Education level scale: This scale consists of 03 values: 1. Education level below university; 2. Undergraduate level; 3. Postgraduate level.

Measurement of monthly income: We built a scale of 05 values reflecting 05 monthly income levels of workers: 1. Under 05 million VND; 2. From 5 to 10 million VND; 3. Over 10 - 15 million VND; 4. Over 15 - 20 million VND; 5. Over 20 million VND. These are the common monthly income levels of young workers in Vietnam.

Data collection and processing

An online questionnaire (using Google Forms) was set up and sent to the research participants. Before answering the questionnaire, they were asked to confirm their agreement to participate in providing data for the research. The survey data was checked and preliminarily processed before statistical analysis. SPSS 26.0 software was used to analyze the data, thereby drawing conclusions and proving the research hypotheses. Statistical analyses were performed in turn, including: frequency and percentage statistics to describe the demographic characteristics of the research sample; reliability and convergent validity of the organizational commitment scale were assessed through Cronbach's Alpha and EFA analysis; mean score and standard deviation statistics to assess the level of organizational commitment of employees;

finally, analysis of differences to explore the influence of age, gender, education level, and income on organizational commitment of young employees in the research sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of research sample

There were a total of 311/350 valid responses from participants, of which 36.7% (114) were male, 62.1% (193) were female, and 1.2% (04) were of other gender. Participants under 25 years old accounted for 66.9% (208), from 25 to under 30 years old were 33.1% (103). 232 participants had a university education level (74.9%), 10.6% (33) had postgraduate level, and 14.8% (46) had below university level. 22.8% (71) of participants were working in the field of Human Resources Administration, 29.6% (92) were working in the field of business, 19.0% (59) were working in the field of education and health, and 28.6% (89) were working in other fields. There are 13.2% (41) of employees working in state agencies, 54.7% (170) working in private enterprises, 13.2% (41) working in joint ventures with foreign countries, 10.3% (32) working in foreign enterprises, and the remaining 8.7% working in other organizations. The monthly income of participants accounts for a large proportion at 5 - 10 million VND (40.2%), 10 million - 15 million (20.9%), over 15 - 20 million (9.3%), over 20 million (4.5%) and 25.1% have a monthly salary of less than 5 million VND.

Cronbach's Alpha and EFA Analysis

The results of the reliability test of the organizational commitment scale through Cronbach's Alpha analysis (15 items) = 0.946 and the Corrected Item-Total Correlation of the items in the scale have values from 0.515 to 0.813. This result shows that the scale has good reliability, no items of the scale were eliminated and continued to be included in the EFA analysis. The results of the EFA analysis show that the observed variables have good measurement values, Factor Loading from 0.342 to 0.694. The KMO coefficient = 0.958 > 0.5, Eigenvalues = 8.150 > 1, total variance extracted = 54.334% (>50%) shows the convergent value of the scale and the suitability of the data set.

Testing research hypotheses

H1. The organizational commitment of young Vietnamese workers is at an average level.

The descriptive statistics from the data set of this study show that the organizational commitment of young workers is generally at a moderate level (Mean = 3.34/5.0, SD = 0.85). There is a statistically significant difference between the three components of organizational commitment (Affective commitment - AC, Normative commitment - NC, Continuance commitment - CC), but the difference is not large ($M_{AC} = 3.40$, $SD = 0.88$; $M_{NC} = 3.31$, $SD = 1.00$; $M_{CC} = 3.26$, $SD = 0.91$) ($p < 0.05$). In these three aspects, affective commitment has a higher statistical score than the other two aspects. From this result, it can be concluded that the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam is not high, which also means that a part of young workers are willing to change their workplace. Several studies on organizational commitment of employees in different contexts in Vietnam also found that employees in general and young employees in particular have low commitment and attachment to the organization, with only above average, many employees intend to leave the enterprise (Tram, 2024; Hue, 2024; Tuan et al., 2025). Several studies by scholars in different countries around the world also show that the organizational commitment of employees is generally limited (Radosavljević et al., 2017; Motsaathebe & Molefi, 2025). These findings raise urgent issues for managers in general and human resource managers in particular to take practical measures

to enhance the organizational commitment of young employees, thereby improving the quality of human resources, ensuring conditions for sustainable development for the organization.

H2: Age, gender, education level, and income have an impact on the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam.

Analysis of the difference in the level of organizational commitment of young workers by gender showed that there was no statistically significant difference ($F = 1.628$, $p = 0.203 > 0.05$), the group of young male workers and the group of young female workers had similar levels of organizational commitment ($M_{\text{males}} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.91$; $M_{\text{females}} = 3.31$, $SD = 0.82$). Thus, gender did not affect the organizational commitment of young workers in the sample of this study. Studies by Ariffin et al. (2015), Gönül & Osman (2018), and Singh et al. (2023) also had similar conclusions: males and females have a similar level of organizational commitment. Some other studies have found, contrary to our study, these studies confirm that the level of organizational commitment of young workers is different between men and women; females are statistically significantly higher on organizational commitment than males (Lalit et al., 2005; Adamchik & Sedlak, 2024); Kumasey (2014), Affum-Osei et al. (2015) found that males were more committed compared to females. From these results, it can be seen that the impact of gender on organizational commitment of young workers depends on the research sample; research samples with different characteristics may have different results.

This study found that age has an impact on the organizational commitment of young employees. There is a statistically significant difference in the level of organizational commitment of employees in different age groups, employees from 25 to under 30 years old have a higher level of organizational commitment than employees under 25 years old ($t = -3.422$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$) ($M_{25 \text{ to under } 30 \text{ years old}} = 3.58$, $SD = 0.84$; $M_{\text{Under } 25 \text{ years old}} = 3.22$; $SD = 0.84$). Similar findings were found in the studies of Naseem et al. (2013), Sangeeta (2018), and Gönül & Osman (2018). In these studies, the authors asserted that employees in older age groups have higher levels of organizational commitment, which is due to their work experience, better adaptation to the working environment, and even achievements and important positions at work, so they change less (Sangeeta, 2018). One-Way ANOVA analysis to test the difference in the level of organizational commitment between the 03 groups of workers with different educational levels showed that there was no statistically significant difference ($F = 1.138$, $p = 0.322 > 0.05$). However, the T-Test between the group of workers with university education and the group with post-graduate education confirmed that there was a difference in the level of organizational commitment between these 02 groups ($t = -2.294$, $p = 0.025 < 0.05$), the group of workers with higher educational levels had a higher level of commitment to the organization ($M_{\text{Postgraduate level}} = 3.51$, $SD = 0.46$; $M_{\text{Undergraduate level}} = 3.30$, $SD = 0.88$). Studies by Ariffin et al. (2015), Novlinda et al. (2018) also confirmed that educational level has a positive influence on employees' organizational commitment. Monthly income is confirmed in this study to have an impact on the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam. Statistical analysis shows that there is a significant difference in the level of organizational commitment of groups of workers with different levels of monthly income ($F = 1.280$, $p = 0.028 < 0.05$). Workers with higher income tend to have higher organizational commitment than others ($M_{\text{Under } 5 \text{ million VND}} = 3.22$, $SD = 0.89$; $M_{\text{From } 5 \text{ to } 10 \text{ million VND}} = 3.30$, $SD = 0.85$; $M_{\text{Over } 10 - 15 \text{ million VND}} = 3.45$, $SD = 0.71$; $M_{\text{Over } 15 - 20 \text{ million VND}} = 0.45$, $SD = 1.10$; $M_{\text{Over } 20 \text{ million VND}} = 3.61$, $SD = 0.61$).

This finding is also confirmed in studies by many authors, when employees have better income and are satisfied with their income, they will be satisfied with their jobs, have better work motivation, participate more actively in their work and tend to be more committed,

attached to the organization, and work more effectively (Meysam & Ali, 2013; Novlinda et al., 2018; Qëndrim, 2020; Li & Chen, 2021; Singh et al., 2023). This result shows that policies related to improving wages and income for employees are necessary and meaningful in enhancing the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam in the current context.

CONCLUSION

A quantitative study with a sample of 311 participants was designed and conducted to explore the level of organizational commitment of young employees in Vietnam and the effects of age, gender, education, and income on their organizational commitment. The results of the study found that the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam is not high, but only at an average level. The results of the study also confirmed that age, education, and monthly income have an impact on the organizational commitment of young workers in Vietnam. Workers with older age, higher education, and higher monthly income have higher levels of organizational commitment than others. From the findings of this study, we believe that to improve the performance of organizations and businesses employing young employees, managers in general and human resource managers in particular need to pay attention and implement appropriate measures and policies to increase the level of organizational commitment of young workers, with special attention paid to solutions and policies to increase opportunities for advanced learning and improve monthly income for workers.

Limitations of the study

This study was designed and conducted as a quantitative study, with a small sample size and a convenient selection. The study only focused on exploring the impact of age, gender, education level, and monthly income on organizational commitment of young workers in the current context of Vietnam, so the research results and findings have certain limitations, limited generalizability, and applicability. For better findings, we recommend further research on a larger sample size, combining quantitative and qualitative research, cross-cultural research, and a wider research scope.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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